

TRADITIONAL METHODS OF STORING GRAIN HARVEST IN THE
END OF THE 19TH CENTURY AND THE 20TH CENTURY
(IN THE EXAMPLE OF SOUTH UZBEKISTAN)

Rahmonov Fakhridin Shoymardonovich

Karshi State University

Associate Professor of the Department of "World History",
PhD in history.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7246796>

Southern Uzbekistan - Kashkadarya and Surhondarya oases, grain crops occupied the main place in Uzbek farms until the 30s of the 20th century. Before planting crops such as wheat, barley, sorghum, and rice, the land is prepared by tilling in the fall. Fields plowed in the spring were plowed lengthwise and crosswise two or more times. Grain is planted in autumn (tromoyi), early spring (bahari). Depending on the amount of weather in dry areas, grain is often sown in the spring. The seed is sown by hand and pressed with a trowel. Wheat fields were irrigated twice: the first time when the grain had just germinated and the second time before earing.

One of the major branches of agriculture in Uzbekistan is grain growing. The main crop in this area is wheat, followed by maize and white sorghum, barley, rice, oats, millet, mung beans, beans, etc. In 1915, more than half of the arable land in Turkestan, 2/3 of the land in Bukhara Emirate and Khiva Khanate was occupied by wheat, mainly three types of wheat were planted.

As in all agricultural oases in the world, timely harvesting of crops grown in South Uzbekistan is one of the most responsible tasks in agriculture. To carry out these tasks on time, special and effective work tools were definitely needed.

At the end of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, in the territory of South Uzbekistan, special methods were used to preserve crops. One of the most widespread methods of crop storage in the region is the method of storage "in the yard". This is a very ancient method [1.], the topography of the land was of particular importance in the preparation of the ora. In some sources, it is reported that the harvest can be stored in such containers for up to three years [2:179],

In the work "Ziroatnama" it is noted that the harvest stored in this way does not lose its quality for up to 50 years [3:18-19.].

In addition, the word "ora" is also mentioned in the work of Mahmud Kashgari as "Oru" [4:115.]. About this method of crop preservation V. P. Nalivkin also cited the example of the residents of the Fergana Valley in his work [5.]. Other

ethnic groups of Central Asia, including the Kyrgyz and Kazakhs, also have the method of keeping the crop in a circle, where it is called "oroo".

The inhabitants of the region also widely used wooden crates to store the harvest. Chests are called "camel chest" in the local dialect, and this method was used more in rich households [6]. This method is more popular among the settled population of the region, because in this method the crop is reliably protected from various rodents. As for the naming of these chests, our senior informants say that these chests were first used by merchants to transport various goods. The name probably originated from the fact that these trunks were transported on camels, which were considered the most convenient means of transportation of that time.

There is also another method of storing crops in the region. In this method, the cloth called "chig" or "chetan" [7], woven from reeds or bamboo, of different sizes, is tied to the edges of the cloth, and tied to the ceiling beams of the rectangular warehouses on all sides, and its wheat or rice is thrown into it. The purpose of this method was to protect grain from pests and rodents [8].

In the Kasbi, Koson, Karshi districts of the Kashkadarya oasis, large hummocks made of clay were used to store the harvest [9.]. The poor farmer stored grain in "rice bags", in a corner of the house, in a special grain store - homma (hompaa), which was made of clay and re-plastered with straw clay. They kept the grains of sesame, flax and other white crops in a hum container. Peas, mash, and rice were stored in kadi containers and used for food when necessary [10.].

Rich people working in the middle and lower part of Kashkadarya had 10 to 40 tanabs of land. In these lands, they used laborers, harvested and threshed the grain, and buried the grain in the threshing floor prepared in their yard ("talaq", ("end"))[11:41] in Hazorasp, Khanka, and Shavat districts. 2.5 and 2.5 1,5 meterwide widths were dug [2:104.].

At the beginning of the 20th century, Rahmatboy from the village of Qataghon in lower Kashkadarya was a rich, wealthy and greedy person who owned at least 30 acres of land. 12-15The peasants performed various jobs: engaged in farming and animal husbandry[12.]. After the grain was reaped, threshed, and threshed, the -wages of the servants were measured. A share (kafsan) was given to the Mullah, Eshon, barber, elder, and Mirab. The rest of the grain was buried in a pit dug in a high and isolated place in the owner's yard. This method of grain storage is called "burying". Linen straw is laid on the bottom of the frame. 10 cm thick linen straw basma-bas is inserted on the sides. In turn, grain was filled. After the sheaves were filled with grain, they were covered with straw and straw

and plastered thickly with straw clay. The top of the fence was 50- above 60 cm the ground. That's why, no matter how much rainfall there is in winter and spring, the water has flowed in all directions. It was possible to preserve grain in such containers for up to three years [2:179.].

But in other areas of the oasis, this method is rarely used. There is another method of storing crops in the region, in which a row of guwala or thin straw walls are rammed into the corner of the barns and covered with straw. Its base is 40-50 cm. a barrier wall made of clay and gouwala with raised posts was built on these posts. This method is also considered very effective. This method is also widespread in the mountainous regions of the oasis, where such harvest storages are called "trench" [13.]. It is worth mentioning here that M. Kashgari's work also mentions this tool used for storing crops in the form of "kenduk", but it is emphasized that it is in the form of hum [4:444].

Farmers of the region used a variety of pumpkin called "pumpkin" (kadi) to store small quantities of beans, sorghum, mash and similar crops. Such harvest-saving pumpkins were called "donkadi" in the Sokh district of the valley [14:78-79].

Therefore, the use of traditional methods of crop preservation in the territory of Southern Uzbekistan was diverse and unique. Archeological evidence also fully confirms that the inhabitants of the region have been using these methods since ancient times. Therefore, the traditional methods of preserving this crop, which have been improved over the centuries, have led to the emergence of several methods by the time being studied.

The existence of such methods as ora, "camel chest", "homma", "piling and burying" and khandak, which are used to store the harvest, can be proof of our above opinion. Since these methods of the local population played an important role in maintaining the quality of the crop, the demand for it has spread to the neighboring areas of the region. Therefore, it is worth noting that the peoples living in the region have developed their own ethnocultural traditions in this field.

In conclusion, it can be said that historical-ethnographic sources and field researches say that in the end of the 19th and 20th centuries, the population of South Uzbekistan had several traditional methods of preserving the grain harvest. quality storage for seeds. Also, grain (mostly barley) was weighed and boiled and given to livestock in winter seasons. Therefore, their activities in agriculture and animal husbandry are also based on simple cooperation. This cooperation eased their hard work a little. The customs formed during this labor

process have an important place in their social life because they satisfy the needs of the peasants.

References:

1. Field records. China village, Sherabad district , 20 20 years .
2. Shaniyazov K. Uzbek - Karluki (Historical-ethnographic essay). - Tashkent: Science, 1964. -195.
3. Mahmud Hassani . Agriculture . - T. , 1991. -76.
4. Mahmud Kashgari. The dictionary is Turkish. - Tashkent, 1960.-500.
5. Nalivkin V. P. Opyt issledovaniya peskov Ferganskoy oblast. - Novyy Margelan, 1887.-229.
6. Field notes. Aparidi village, Guzor district , 20 2 0 year .
7. Field records. Orta village, Yakkabog district , 20 2 0 year .
8. Field notes. Chim village, Qamashi district , 20 2 0 year .
9. Field notes. Moglan and Khojakasbi villages, K asbi district , 20 2 0 year .
10. Field notes. Qamashi district, Chim village, 2020.
11. Sazonova M.V. Traditsionnoe hozyaystvo Uzbek Yuzhnogo Khorezma. - M.: Nauka, 1978. -97.
12. Field records. Qatagon village, Kasbi district, 2020.
13. Field records. Aspidukhtar village , Kitab district, 2020.
14. Djakhanov U. Zemledelie tajikov doliny Sokha v kontse XIX - nachale XX vv. Dushanbe. Donish, 1989. -152.

